

Achieving Sustainable Energy Development in Benin using OSeMOSYS

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Executive Summary

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of Benin's energy future, examining three scenarios Business as Usual (BAU), Government Energy Target Case 1 (GET Case 1), and Government Energy Target Case 2 (GET Case 2) spanning from 2015 to 2070. The study focuses on installed capacity, renewable energy integration, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, providing insights into the pathways Benin could take to achieve energy self-sufficiency, universal electricity access, and emissions reductions.

The analysis shows a significant increase in installed capacity across all scenarios, particularly in solar photovoltaic (PV) energy, which emerges as the cornerstone of Benin's renewable energy strategy. Solar PV stands out as the most promising and cost-effective technology, playing a dominant role in energy generation from 2040 onwards. In contrast, offshore wind energy remains nonexistent across all scenarios, reflecting the absence of its development in Benin's energy landscape.

In the BAU scenario, installed capacity will reach approximately 23 GW by 2070, with modest growth driven by existing trends. The GET Case 1 scenario, which aims for 35.14% renewable energy integration by 2030 and the elimination of electricity imports, will increase capacity to 30 GW by 2070. GET Case 2, which builds on Case 1 by targeting 100% electricity access, projects an installed capacity of 33 GW by the same year.

Natural gas, particularly combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT), remains a critical component of the energy mix in all scenarios, indicating that despite the push for renewables, gas will continue to play a significant role in Benin's energy strategy. However, the reliance on fossil fuels in the GET scenarios limits the potential for significant GHG emissions reductions, even as renewable energy integration increases. This highlights the need for a more aggressive approach to renewables beyond the 35.14% target to achieve meaningful emissions reductions.

The study underscores the importance of a diversified energy mix for ensuring energy security and reducing dependency on any single source. It recommends prioritizing investment in solar PV, including utility-scale and distributed systems with storage capabilities, and exploring energy storage solutions to manage intermittency. Additionally, the study calls for policies that ensure a stable natural gas supply, promote energy efficiency across all sectors, and explore carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies for future emissions reductions.

1. Introduction

Recently, the global shift towards net-zero emissions has gained widespread recognition. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the international community have demonstrated that climate change is closely linked to anthropogenic emissions, which have already caused a global temperature increase of 1.1°C compared to pre-industrial levels (IRENA WETO, 2022). The energy system, as one of the primary contributors to the climate crisis, is responsible for nearly 90% of total carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and around 75% of total greenhouse gas emissions (COP26 Report, 2021). The transition from fossil fuel-based energy to clean energy has become a global priority, particularly in Africa, where the challenge of electricity access remains significant (Climate Watch Historical GHG Emissions, 2021).

The Republic of Benin, a developing country in Sub-Saharan Africa, faces a significant challenge in energy access. The electricity access rate is 38.36% according to the Benin Energy System (SIE-Benin). The country's energy system is heavily reliant on biomass, which accounted for 54% of primary energy consumption in 2017, with hydrocarbon imports at 43.1% and electricity at 1.9% (SIE-Benin, 2017). Despite abundant energy resources, Benin continues to rely on traditional fossil-fuel energy sources and is highly dependent on electricity imports from neighbouring countries, particularly Nigeria and Ghana (Benin-SEforALL Africa Hub, 2022). Moreover, the country is experiencing rapid growth in energy demand, driven by population growth, urbanization, and economic development. The recent industrial zone, commissioned in 2022, covering 1,640 hectares of land (GDIZ: Un Nouveau Pôle Économique au Bénin, 2024), would considerably increase the electricity demand of the country.

Mitigating the threat of climate change and expanding energy access are key objectives of both SDG 7 on energy access and the Paris Agreement on climate change (IPCC, 2022). In response, the Government of Benin has set an ambitious goal to achieve self-sufficiency in electricity supply by 2026, with the integration of 35% renewable energy by 2030 (PAGs 2016-2021 and 2021-2026; PANER 2015). From nearly negligible renewable energy installed capacity (0.9% in 2016), the country has increased its renewable energy share to 16.45% by 2022, out of a total grid-installed capacity of 152 MW in 2023. This capacity is projected to more than triple to 513 MW, with approximately 30% renewable energy by 2026 (Benin Electricity Production Company, 2024). These targets aim to achieve electricity self-sufficiency and increase renewable energy integration, improving the current energy mix with environmental considerations.

This study aims to evaluate various energy production scenarios for long-term capacity expansion to guide the Republic of Benin's transition pathways, considering electricity access and the government's targets. The research explores optimal pathways for capacity expansion, maximizing renewable energy integration, and enhancing system flexibility to meet future demand sustainably. Key questions include a measured assessment of the future energy landscape considering Benin's current energy policies, frameworks, and plans, effective capacity expansion planning to meet the Government Energy Target (GET) by 2030, and pathways to achieving net-zero emissions by 2070.

2. Methodology

Data collection and calibration involved gathering comprehensive information across multiple sectors of energy demand, supply, technology, emissions, policies, and socioeconomic indicators from various sources such as utility companies, national energy reports from the Ministry of Energy and Mines of Benin, and the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). The dataset includes techno-economic parameters of supply-side technologies, installed capacities, emission factors, and final electricity demands. Additionally, national data such as energy consumption patterns and generation capacities were also included. Hereby, the open data "Starter Kits" for Benin, which include essential data and information that can be directly imported into the Open-Source energy MOdelling SYStem (OSeMOSYS) model, was used in this study (Allington et. al, 2023). This facilitated the quick initiation of creating energy scenarios.

OSeMOSYS was used to perform this study. It is an open-source, bottom-up energy modelling system designed for long-term energy planning and capacity expansion analysis. It is widely used to evaluate various energy production scenarios and to formulate optimal pathways for sustainable energy transitions. The model offers a comprehensive representation of technologies and energy flows within a system, taking into account performance metrics, costs, resource utilization, and environmental impacts (Howells et al., 2011).

Three scenarios are explored in this study: Business as Usual (BAU), Government Energy Target case 1 (GET) and the GET with 100% (GET 100% EA) electricity access.

- **Baseline (BAU) Scenario:** The pace of power plant commissioning continues as it is currently, without any accelerated efforts to increase capacity or shift to cleaner technologies. Electricity Access: The electricity access rate improves gradually, but there is no significant push towards universal access by 2030. Emissions are expected to continue rising as energy demand grows, driven by population and economic growth, without any significant policy interventions or technology shifts.
- **The Government Energy Target: Case 1 (GET):** In this scenario, the goal is to achieve self-sufficiency in electricity production, reducing or eliminating dependence on electricity imports from neighbouring countries while integrating 35.14% renewable energy (RE) into the energy mix by 2030. The emissions are expected to decrease compared to the BAU scenario.
- **Government Energy Target: Case 2 (GET 100% EA):** Similar to Case 1, it is built on Case 1 by maintaining the goal of 35.14% renewable energy integration by 2030. The critical difference in Case 2 is the emphasis on achieving 100% electricity access by 2030, ensuring that every household in Benin has access to electricity. This scenario is likely to result in slightly higher emissions than Case 1 due to the increased energy demand required to achieve full electricity access.

Figure 1: Three scenarios of the modelling

3. Results

Figure 2 shows an increase in installed capacity for all the scenarios from 2020 to 2070. There is a significant increase in solar PV and almost steady installed capacity for hydropower due to the limited potential of Benin in hydropower. Offshore Wind is inexistent across all scenarios.

On the other side, gas power plants, especially combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT), maintain a presence across three scenarios, highlighting the role of natural gas in power production with the current trend and government target by the horizon of 2030 ensuring electricity production with less emissions concerning the dustier energy sources (coal and oil). Moreover, the scenarios depict a diversified energy mix, with a balance of solar, wind, gas, and hydropower, which is essential for ensuring energy security and reducing dependency on any single source.

The BAU, GET case 1 and GET case 2, account respectively for about 1.2 GW, 1.4 GW and 1.75 GW by the target year 2030 and these capacities will increase to 23 GW, 30 GW and 33 GW by 2070. The gap needs to be filled by shifting from the BAU to GET case 1 is just 0.2 GW whereas, this gap increases up to 0.35 for the GET case 2 ensuring the current energy per capita (111,8 kWh) for all the population in Benin by 2030 while achieving 35.14% of renewable integration.

Figure 2: Total installed capacity for the scenarios from 2020 to 2070

In all the scenarios, energy generation increases in tandem with demand growth, with the main renewable technology which solar PV as shown in Figure 3. This shows that Benin has significant potential in solar PV seen as the most cost-effective technology for it is the main source of generation from 2040 to 2070 across all the scenarios. The Generation of BAU increases from about 150 PJ to 215 PJ for GET case 1 and about 280 PJ for GET case 2 by 2070.

Figure 3: Power generation for the scenarios from 2020 to 2070

While the objective of the GET scenarios aims to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in the long term compared to the BAU, the reduction was limited due to the remaining reliance on fossil fuels, even as renewables are integrated due to the target of self-sufficiency by 2030, mainly by having its generation to substitute the electricity imports and the weak share of renewable (35,14%) for GET case 1 as it can be noticed in figure 4. The decrease in emissions expected has been slightly reversed from 2024 to 2030 while GET case 2 shows a bit more emissions compared with the BAU and the GET case 1. This can be explained by the increase in energy demand to fill 61.3% of the population without electricity, the generation of about 65% out of just 35% Renewables of fossil-based energy is to cover the amount of electricity imports in BAU climate change scenarios, emissions are seen to increase over time due to the prevalence of thermal generation and demand growth. Hence, Benin needs more renewables integrations to meet the CO₂ emissions reduction while solving the electricity import dependency and electricity access issue.

Figure 4: Total Emissions for the three scenarios from 2015 to 2070

However, as shown in Figure 5 below, the implementation of the policy of GET case 1 requires 1.03 times the total discounted costs for BAU and 1.08 times for the GET to achieve 100% electricity access. Those two costs are respectively about 4.2 billion and 4.4 billion, meaning the difference of 0.2 billion is the financial impact of shifting from GET case 1 to GET case 2.

Figure 5: Total discounted costs for the scenarios from 2020 to 2070

4. Discussion

The significant increase in solar PV capacity across all scenarios highlights its potential as the cornerstone of Benin's renewable energy strategy. Investment in utility-scale and distributed solar PV systems, including those with storage capabilities, should be prioritized. Policies that incentivize solar PV adoption, reduce the cost of solar technology, and streamline the approval process for solar projects are recommended.

Furthermore, Energy Security should be analysed for Gas Power Plants. The continued reliance on gas power plants, particularly combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT), suggests that natural gas will play a crucial role in the scenarios BAU, GET case and GET case 2. Policies should focus on ensuring a stable and sustainable supply of natural gas, while also exploring carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies to minimize emissions from gas power plants in the future.

Although hydropower shows steady capacity, its limited potential in Benin necessitates exploring other renewable sources like wind offshore or improving existing hydropower facilities for better efficiency. Investment in micro and small hydropower projects could also be considered for rural electrification.

Moreover, With the increase in solar PV, energy storage becomes essential for managing intermittency. Exploration of battery storage, pumped hydro, and other energy storage technologies should be encouraged. Policies could include subsidies for energy storage projects or research grants for innovative storage solutions.

About energy efficiency, as demand grows, energy efficiency measures across all sectors (industrial, residential, and commercial) will be critical. Policies promoting energy-efficient appliances, buildings, and industrial processes could help curb the increase in energy demand.

The total investment costs of achieving the GET case 1 and case 2 respectively 41.9 and 44 billion USD are significant, meaning that a lot of investment is to be mobilized to fulfil this target.

The target set by the Government of Benin in renewable integration does not achieve the CO2 emissions reduction compared with the BAU due to the share of fossil fuel energy needed to compensate for electricity imports. Moreover, the target to achieve simultaneously electricity self-sufficiency and 100% electricity access by 2030 even including 35.14% renewables, though it is ambitious, is not aligned with CO2 reduction. More renewable energy is needed to pave the way for energy transition.

Limitations of the Study

The study relies on available data, which might not capture all variables or the latest technological advancements. This could limit the accuracy of the projections. The scenarios are based on certain assumptions about future technology costs, resource availability, and policy developments. The study results reflect the trends and pace in the energy sector of Benin, however, the lack of accurate data and the assumptions made could affect the results, leaving room for further exploration. The study assumes no development in onshore wind, which might overlook potential opportunities, particularly as technology advances and costs decrease.

While the study highlights the total costs, it may not fully consider the challenges related to financing, such as securing investment, interest rates, and economic stability.

Concerning the environmental and social Impacts, the study focuses on technical and economic aspects, with limited consideration of environmental and social impacts, such as land use conflicts or impacts on biodiversity for very large-scale PV deployment.

Exploring the feasibility and potential of onshore wind which is more than the offshore one in Benin is a potential area for future research. Modelling the energy-clean transition pathways for Benin including different scenarios with sensitivity analysis is paramount since the government target has shown that the country will still emit more CO2 in the future than the current trend of emissions. Further research could assess the flexibility of integrating

RE technologies into Benin's national grid based on this study's findings. Green hydrogen pathways and their massive deployment could constitute an area for future research to complement the present study.

5. Conclusion

This study examines Benin's energy future through three scenarios: Business as Usual (BAU), Government Energy Target Case 1 (GET Case 1), and Government Energy Target Case 2 (GET Case 2). The analysis reveals a significant rise in installed capacity across all scenarios, with solar PV emerging as the dominant renewable energy source. However, the limited potential for hydropower and the absence of offshore wind highlight the need for diversified renewable investments. Natural gas remains vital for energy security, particularly through combined-cycle gas turbines (CCGT).

By 2070, installed capacities are projected at 23 GW for BAU, 30 GW for GET Case 1, and 33 GW for GET Case 2. While these targets indicate progress toward energy self-sufficiency, the reliance on fossil fuels hinders significant reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Achieving 100% electricity access by 2030 (GET Case 2) demands substantial investments, with costs estimated at \$44 billion.

Benin must prioritize more aggressive renewable energy integration, particularly solar PV, supported by investments in energy storage and efficiency. Stronger policy frameworks are needed to meet both energy security and climate goals, ensuring a sustainable and resilient energy future.

This study recommends policymakers in Benin prioritise the expansion of solar PV as a cornerstone of the energy strategy, supported by investments in energy storage to manage intermittency. Strengthen policies that incentivize renewable energy adoption, streamline approval processes, and promote energy efficiency across sectors. Additionally, ensure a stable natural gas supply while exploring carbon capture and storage (CCS) technologies to reduce emissions. Given the significant investment required to meet energy targets, fostering public-private partnerships and securing international funding will be essential for achieving sustainable energy development and reducing dependency on fossil fuels.

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